

Supplementary information

CRISPR/nCas9-based genome editing on GM2 gangliosidoses fibroblasts via non-viral vectors

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Supplementary Table 1. List of primers used in this study. The sequences for MfeI and MluI enzymes are highlighted in yellow and green, respectively.
*Sequences correspond to Leal & Alméciga, 2022 [1].

Purpose	Target	Forward (5' to 3')	Reverse (5' to 3')
HEXA ORF amplification	HEXA	CGATCAATTGATGGCAAGCTCCAGGCTT	ATCGACGCGTGGTCTGTTCAAACCTCCTG
HEXB ORF amplification	HEXB	CGATCAATTGATGGAGCTGTGCGGGCTG	ATCGACGCGTCATGTTCTCATGGTTACAA- TATCCAGC
*Homologous recombination assay	AAVS1-Out	TTCGATTGGAGTCGCTTTAACTG	-
	CMV	-	AGCTCTGCTTATATAGACCTCC

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Supplementary Figure 1. MTT and LDH assays. The figure shows the % of cell viability of GM2 fibroblasts after their interaction with 25µg/mL/0.05mg/mL MNPs@Ag-pD/BUF-II:liposome for 48 hours.

Supplementary Figure 2. Nitric oxide determination. The figure shows the effect of the long-term CRISPR/nCas9-based genome edition on GM2 fibroblasts. Positive control corresponds to the incubation of fibroblasts with 1 μ M lipopolysaccharide *Escherichia coli* O111:B4.

Supplementary references

1. Leal, A.F. and C.J. Alméciga-Díaz, *Efficient CRISPR/Cas9 nickase-mediated genome editing in an in vitro model of mucopolysaccharidosis IVA*. *Gene Ther*, 2022.